

CLERKSROOM
BARRISTERS & MEDIATORS DIRECT

Title: Introducing Billy Bot, the worlds first robotic chatbot AI junior clerk for barristers chambers.

Name: Jonathan Maskew

Business Development Director, Clerksroom Direct, England,UK

INTRODUCTION:

The concept of Billy Bot came out of the huge growth in public access work that now comes directly to barristers for legal advice and representation in court. Members of the public can now contact barristers directly and discuss potential cases with the clerks in chambers. This presents a new difficulty for barristers' clerks as they need to spend much more time dealing with enquiries than they do with solicitors or other lawyers who make contact to obtain advice and book a barrister for a hearing or for advice.

AIM:

The aim of Billy Bot is simple. Billy will have total access to chambers systems and can be programmed to take instructions, quote fees, carry out conflict checks, create new cases and book the cases into the diary system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

We have duplicated databases for chambers, courts and barristers at other chambers we work with. The data protection, secure site certification and payment gateway integration is also pretty complicated. This is where API's come in. API allow the creation of applications which access the features or data of an operating system, application, or other service." according to google. So the concept of Billy Bot, the cheeky chappie junior clerk robot is simple but the actual integration of the various data systems is far more complicated. The key to making it work is to understand what you are trying to achieve in the first instance. With Billy Bot, the solution was clear. We wanted to remove many of the simple and repetitive tasks from our staff to free them up to do more productive tasks.

RESULTS:

Billy is in the process of taking new enquiries, add it into the case management system, carry out a conflict check, create the booking and send confirmation is 167 clicks, keystrokes and so on. We currently do that 1,500 times a month, so that's 250,000 clicks and keystrokes. The bit

that needs an experienced clerk is the allocation of the case to the most suited barrister and to agree the fee or budget with the solicitor.

CONCLUSIONS:

It is very early days for Billy and he is a long term project, ending up with experimenting with AI. For now, Billy is a functional chat bot able to take instructions and book cases into our various I.T. systems. The immediate plan is to widen Billy's functionality and then deploy him to all of our websites. Once on all of our sites and working correctly, we can then deploy him to partner sites. We currently have 100 partners all directing enquiries to us. Billy is free, works 24/7, never complains, never takes holidays or sick leave and he can be instantly replicated. Using unique API keys for each deployment, we can track ROI which makes the entire project very exciting.

KEYWORDS:

Artificial Intelligence, AI , Chatbot, Chatbots, Legaltech, Legal Disruption

BIOGRAPHY:

Jonathan Maskew has been involved in the management and business development strategies for barristers and chambers spanning over 25 years and provides his expertise and skills across our various teams.

Possessing a proven array of leadership, management and business development skills required to drive business forward in an increasingly competitive market place, his focus is on maintaining and building strong relationships, excellent client service models and delivery levels for all clients who are better informed than ever and expect nothing less.

He is recognised as a dynamic, inspirational, influential, personable leader with a "can-do" attitude and widely acknowledged with having highly developed networking skills, possessing consummate interpersonal skills with a view to creating sustainable, valued and trusted relationships for the benefit of clients in line with our strategy, mission, culture and values.

Jonathan plays an active role on social media and the route for business online where clients are engaging in new and exciting ways including the increasing use of legaltech, artificial intelligence and chatbots.